

GENDER EQUALITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article discusses the reforms being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to achieve gender equality, their effectiveness, and focuses on the protection of the rights of women living in the country and the creation of adequate conditions for them. It is also intended to provide suggestions that provide the right solutions to existing problems.

Key words: Gender equality, feminism, equal rights, violence, United Nations, resolutions of Cabinet of Ministers, democracy, society, harmonization, state structures, female ministers, female mayors

Gender equality and sexual equality, more precisely: equality between men and women, is a concept that implies the achievement of equal rights between men and women in the family and other legal relationships. According to some researchers, gender equality is the next stage of socio-sexual relations after the patriarchal system. The principle of gender equality is to study and eliminate all social barriers that prevent a person from emerging as a person, as well as to create equal social opportunities for realizing the personality of men and women in all spheres of life. Uzbekistan began participating in the list of gender equality indicators from 2019. According to the status of 2019, the gender equality indicator of Uzbekistan took the 62nd place among 189 countries on the list. According to experts of the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), 29 women out of every 100,000 in Uzbekistan die due to gender inequality, and the birth rate for every thousand adolescent girls aged 15-19 is 23.8. According to the UN, Uzbekistan ranked 57 out of 188 countries in the ranking of countries by gender equality in 2019.

Globally, women earn 10 per cent of the world's income but work two-thirds of the world's working hours. At the same time, 70 per cent of the world's poor are women.

Women play a significant role in the issues of sustainable development and economic wellbeing. Gender equality is one of the fundamental human rights, reflected in SDGs. UNFPA promotes equality of rights and opportunities for men and women, and calls for implementing necessary legal and political reforms in this area. In addition, we support collecting gender-disaggregated data and implement initiatives aimed at empowering women and combating gender-based violence.

Uzbekistan has been among the first Central Asian countries to ratify the CEDAW – UN Convention on Elimination of all Forms of Violence and Discrimination against Women. To date, the country has submitted four periodical reports to CEDAW Committee. In response to recommendations received to latest report, National Action Plan on CEDAW was adopted, and UNFPA is working to bring together the efforts of national institutions and international organizations in implementing the Plan.

In addition, UNFPA contributes to development of effective gender-related legislation in the country. With the Fund's support, draft Law on equality of rights and opportunities for men and women was developed and reviewed by international expert. The draft is currently being submitted to national lawmaking bodies for further processing. In recent years, the Government of Uzbekistan has been prioritizing improvement of legislative and institutional base for further ensuring equality for women in all spheres of life. With the introduction of 30% quota in Parliament for women candidates of political parties, more women could be elected and participate in decision-making. UNFPA is committed to supporting the government in these efforts, with advocacy and capacity-building activities for local experts. With UNFPA's help, several centres for social and legal support of women were established in the country. The Fund provided training on gender-based violence prevention for professionals from different areas including community leaders, psychologists and law enforcement system representatives.

Giving Choices to Women in Crisis Situations – UNFPA-supported Helpdesk Opens in Tashkent

Otabek, 27, lives in the old city neighborhood in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. He has been brought up in a rather traditional family, taught from his early childhood that men are stronger and smarter, while women's place is at home, with children and house chores. Never in his life could Otabek imagine that a day will come when he, no longer able to cope with conflicts in his family, will take his young wife, his mother and unmarried sisters to a counselor for psychological advice.

The Women's Helpdesk opened in Tashkent and two other Uzbek cities in January last year, within a joint project of Civic Initiatives Support Fund and EU's TACIS Programme. Starting from this year, UNFPA took on EU's baton in supporting of the Helpdesk in Tashkent, providing administrative support with equipment, facilities and staff, and also assisting in organizing of training and advocacy events for the staff and clients.

To advance systemic and transformative changes in gender equality and women empowerment in Uzbekistan, UNDP is focused on the following priority areas:

- Transforming gender bias and stereotypes to expand women's political and economic participation;
- Improving the system of gender disaggregated data and analysis for policy-making;
- Promoting inclusive employment and decent job opportunities;
- Preventing and responding to gender-based violence;
- Advocating for gender-responsive digital and green transitions; and
- Promoting gender equality in government agencies through the introduction of a Gender Equality Seal for public institutions in Uzbekistan. The State Customs Committee was the first public institution in Uzbekistan to embrace the initiative.
- Addressing gender-biased stereotypes through amending the legislation, raising awareness and empowering women leaders;
- Improving socio-economic conditions and opportunities for women through enhancing their employment opportunities, including by promoting STEM initiatives; and

- Improving the system of collection, analysis and regular monitoring of the gender-disaggregated data on women's public and socio-economic participation, gender-based violence through developing methodologies for data collection and analysis and creating special digital tools for this in accordance with the provisions of the UN Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW).

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